

BOOSTED LIGHTWEIGHT ENSEMBLE LEARNING FOR MULTI-CLASS CHEST X-RAY CLASSIFICATION

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Abstract

Rapid and reliable identification of respiratory diseases from chest X-ray images remains an important task in computer-aided medical diagnosis. This study proposes a lightweight, ensemble-based boosting framework for multi-class classification of chest X-ray images into COVID-19, pneumonia, and normal categories. The proposed method integrates three efficient convolutional neural network architectures, namely DenseNet121, MobileNetV2, and NASNetMobile, and combines their outputs through a boosted ensemble mechanism to improve predictive performance while preserving computational efficiency. The dataset was split into training, validation, and test sets, and the images were resized, normalised, and augmented prior to model training. Experimental results showed that the proposed boosted ensemble model achieved a classification accuracy of **97.40%**, outperforming the individual base models DenseNet121 (**91.60%**), MobileNetV2 (**94.40%**), and NASNetMobile (**93.46%**). These findings indicate that boosted lightweight ensemble learning can provide an effective and practical solution for automated chest X-ray image classification in medical imaging applications.

Keywords: chest X-ray; COVID-19; pneumonia; deep learning; ensemble learning; boosted learning; lightweight CNN; medical image classification

1. Introduction

Chest X-ray imaging is one of the most accessible and widely used radiological tools for the diagnosis of pulmonary diseases, including COVID-19 and pneumonia [1]-[5]. Its low cost, rapid acquisition, and broad clinical availability make it especially valuable for screening and routine diagnostic workflows [1], [3]. However, interpreting chest X-ray images can be challenging because disease-related radiographic manifestations may overlap across different pathological categories. Diagnostic inconsistency may also arise from inter-observer variability and differences in clinical experience [1], [5].

Recent developments in artificial intelligence have significantly improved the automatic analysis of medical images. In particular, convolutional neural networks have shown strong performance in classification tasks involving chest radiography [1]-[5]. These models can learn complex visual patterns directly from image data and have therefore been widely investigated

for disease detection and decision-support applications [1], [4, 5]. Nevertheless, individual CNN models may remain sensitive to dataset characteristics, overfit specific image features, and not generalise robustly across cases.

Ensemble learning is an effective strategy for addressing these limitations. By combining outputs from multiple models, ensemble methods can reduce prediction variance, exploit complementary feature representations, and improve robustness [2]-[5]. At the same time, lightweight architectures are desirable for practical deployment because they reduce computational cost and support use in resource-constrained environments [4], [6, 7].

In this work, a lightweight, ensemble-based boosting framework is proposed for classifying chest X-ray images into COVID-19, pneumonia, and normal classes. The framework combines DenseNet121, MobileNetV2, and NASNetMobile as base models and integrates their predictions via a boosted ensemble. The study aims to improve diagnostic accuracy while maintaining a model that is efficient for real-world implementation. The main contributions of this work are as follows. First, a lightweight multi-model deep learning framework is developed for three-class chest X-ray classification. Second, a boosted ensemble strategy is used to enhance predictive performance beyond that of individual base models. Third, the proposed method is experimentally validated and shown to achieve higher accuracy than each constituent CNN model.

2. Related Work

Deep learning has become one of the dominant approaches for automated chest X-ray analysis [1]-[5]. Earlier studies commonly employed single CNN architectures such as VGG, ResNet, DenseNet, and MobileNet for detecting lung abnormalities and respiratory diseases [1], [5]. These methods demonstrated that transfer learning from large-scale natural image datasets can be effectively adapted to radiological classification tasks [1], [3]-[5].

DenseNet-based architectures are widely used in medical imaging due to their efficient feature reuse and strong gradient propagation [8]. MobileNet-based models are also attractive because they provide lightweight inference with competitive accuracy, making them suitable for deployment-oriented diagnostic systems [6]. Similarly, NASNetMobile offers an efficient design derived through neural architecture search and has shown promise in classification tasks where both performance and efficiency are important [7].

Although single-model systems have achieved encouraging results, they may not fully capture the diverse imaging characteristics present in multi-class chest X-ray data [1]-[5]. Ensemble learning has therefore been explored as a means of improving performance by aggregating predictions from multiple base models [2]-[5]. Such methods can reduce individual model bias and improve robustness by combining complementary representations [2], [3].

Despite these advances, many existing studies either focus on computationally intensive architectures or assess multiple ensemble variants without focusing on a single, efficient, deployment-oriented solution. In contrast, the present study focuses specifically on boosted lightweight ensemble learning and investigates its effectiveness for combining three efficient CNN models in a unified chest X-ray classification framework.

3. Materials and Methods

3.1 Overall Framework

The proposed framework consists of three stages: base model training, probability prediction, and boosted ensemble fusion. In the first stage, chest X-ray images are used to fine-

tune three pretrained lightweight CNN architectures: DenseNet121, MobileNetV2, and NASNetMobile. Each model is trained for the three-class classification task and produces class probabilities for COVID-19, pneumonia, and normal.

In the second stage, the trained models independently generate softmax probability outputs for each input image. In the third stage, these outputs are combined through a boosted ensemble strategy to obtain the final class prediction. This design enables the proposed framework to leverage complementary model characteristics while mitigating the limitations of relying on a single classifier. The overall workflow of the proposed method is illustrated in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1. Overall workflow of the proposed boosted lightweight ensemble framework for multi-class chest X-ray classification.

3.2 Dataset and Preprocessing

The experiments were conducted on the publicly available Chest X-ray (Covid-19 & Pneumonia) dataset from Kaggle [9]. The dataset contains 6,432 chest X-ray images belonging to three classes: COVID-19, pneumonia, and normal. For this study, the dataset was split into 80% for training, 10% for validation, and 10% for testing for model development and evaluation. All images were resized to 224×224 pixels and normalised before training. To improve generalisation and reduce overfitting, data augmentation techniques, including horizontal flipping, slight rotation, and zooming, were applied during preprocessing.

3.3 Base CNN Models

Three lightweight CNN architectures were selected as base classifiers in the proposed ensemble framework. DenseNet121 was used because its dense connectivity encourages feature reuse and facilitates effective information flow across layers. MobileNetV2 was selected for its computational efficiency and suitability for lightweight deployment scenarios. NASNetMobile was included because it offers an efficient architecture discovered via neural architecture search and balances accuracy and model complexity. Each model was fine-tuned by appending global average pooling and dense softmax classification layers for three-class prediction.

3.4 Boosted Ensemble Learning

The main contribution of the study lies in the boosted ensemble mechanism used to integrate the outputs of the three base models. After each CNN produces a probability distribution over the target classes, the predictions are fused through a boosted ensemble strategy to generate the final decision.

This approach improves classification performance by aggregating complementary information learned by different architectures and reducing reliance on a single model's

behaviour. It also improves robustness in difficult classification cases and supports more stable final decisions.

3.5 Calibration and Evaluation Metrics

To improve confidence calibration, softmax logits from the base models were calibrated using temperature scaling with $T = 3.0$. This step helps reduce overconfidence in predictions and supports more reliable probability estimates before fusion. Model performance was evaluated using accuracy, confusion matrix analysis, and ROC-AUC, which together provide a comprehensive assessment of classification quality.

4. Results

4.1 Quantitative Performance Comparison

The quantitative comparison between the individual base models and the proposed boosted ensemble model is presented in **Table 1** and **Fig. 2**. Among the individual CNNs, MobileNetV2 achieved the best performance with **94.40%** accuracy, followed by NASNetMobile with **93.46%** and DenseNet121 with **91.60%**. The proposed boosted lightweight ensemble model achieved **97.40%** accuracy, outperforming all three base classifiers.

These findings show that the proposed ensemble strategy effectively combines the strengths of the constituent lightweight CNN models, yielding a clear performance gain over individual architectures.

Table 1. Accuracy comparison between individual base models and the proposed boosted ensemble model.

Model	Accuracy (%)
DenseNet121	91.60
MobileNetV2	94.40
NASNetMobile	93.46
Proposed Boosted Lightweight Ensemble	97.40

Fig. 2. Accuracy comparison of DenseNet121, MobileNetV2, NASNetMobile, and the proposed boosted ensemble model.

4.2 Confusion Matrix Analysis

The confusion matrix of the proposed boosted ensemble model is shown in **Fig. 3**. Most images were correctly assigned to their true categories, indicating strong predictive

consistency across the three classes. The confusion matrix also helps identify the relatively small number of misclassified cases and provides insight into class-specific error patterns.

Fig. 3. Confusion matrix of the proposed boosted lightweight ensemble model.

4.3 ROC Curve Analysis

The ROC curves and class-wise AUC values of the proposed model are shown in **Fig. 4**. The ROC analysis indicates strong class discrimination capability across different threshold settings. It confirms the suitability of the proposed framework for multi-class chest X-ray image classification.

Fig. 4. ROC curves and AUC values for the proposed boosted lightweight ensemble model.

4.4 Visual Examples

Representative visual results are presented in **Figs. 5 and 6**. Misclassified samples are shown in **Fig. 5**, while correctly classified examples are shown in **Fig. 6**. These figures provide qualitative insight into both the strengths and limitations of the proposed model. Most errors occur in challenging cases in which radiographic features of COVID-19 and pneumonia are visually similar.

Fig. 5. Representative misclassified chest X-ray images with predicted and true labels.

Fig. 6. Representative correctly classified chest X-ray images with predicted class labels.

5. Discussion

The obtained results confirm the effectiveness of boosted lightweight ensemble learning for chest X-ray classification. Although each base model provided reasonable performance, the proposed ensemble framework achieved the best overall accuracy. This improvement suggests that the three selected CNN architectures capture complementary discriminative information, which is better exploited when their outputs are integrated via boosting. An additional advantage of the proposed framework is its practical efficiency. Since DenseNet121, MobileNetV2, and NASNetMobile are relatively lightweight compared with heavier deep learning architectures, the method remains more suitable for deployment-oriented

environments. This makes the framework relevant for computer-aided diagnosis scenarios where both inference efficiency and predictive reliability are important.

Despite the strong results, some limitations remain. A small number of misclassifications still occur, particularly in cases with overlapping radiographic characteristics between COVID-19 and pneumonia. Future work may therefore include validation on larger and more diverse datasets, the use of external hospital data, and the investigation of more advanced feature fusion or calibration strategies.

6. Conclusion

This study presented a lightweight, boosted ensemble learning framework for multi-class classification of chest X-ray images into COVID-19, pneumonia, and normal categories. By integrating DenseNet121, MobileNetV2, and NASNetMobile through a boosted fusion strategy, the proposed method achieved **97.40%** classification accuracy, outperforming the individual base models DenseNet121 (**91.60%**), MobileNetV2 (**94.40%**), and NASNetMobile (**93.46%**).

The results demonstrate that boosted lightweight ensemble learning can improve classification performance while preserving computational practicality. The proposed framework, therefore, represents a promising solution for computer-aided chest X-ray diagnosis and may be useful in real-world medical imaging applications. Future research should focus on broader validation and further strengthen the framework's robustness.

Adabiyotlar, References, Литературы:

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